

Scelotes limpopoensis Limpopo burrowing skink

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Reptile

Size: 10-20 cm (total body length)

Distribution:

Endemic to southern Africa, including South Africa (Limpopo River Valley, northern Limpopo Province), southern Zimbabwe, and Botswana

Importance:

It serves as an important model species in specific limb development stages in the *Scelotes* genus (intermediate limb development stage, with forelimb digit = 2-3, hindlimb digit number = 4) and is used to study genomic evolution of vertebrates. It has a restricted distribution, occurring in distinct habitats and regions, making them excellent model species for biogeographic and molecular ecology studies.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 26.19 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 3.27 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.22 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: <80%

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 24.88 kilobases

Contig number: 65 311

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